

Safety and Driving Awareness in Connected Vehicles in 5G Enabled Infrastructures

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Abstract

Driving Safety & Awareness requires access in real-time to data which can be used to enforce safety on the road. Based on data transmitted by vehicles and roadside infrastructure, the risk of accidents can be mitigated which will impact costs for society. Current approaches for Misbehavior detection mainly require large amounts of data to train. Additionally, they can be prone to errors and biases and can be difficult to interpret and explain. With 5G-enabled infrastructure Connected and automated mobility (CAM) services provide improved transportation safety and efficiency. This paper discusses a Misbehavior Detection system (MBD) called the DMS system that communicates with the MEC and a 5GMETA platform to share sensor data and alert third-party clients using a third-party service Parking Lot Detector (PLD) as a first response to indicate the nearest parking spot available in case of an emergency.

Keywords: 5G, MEC, Cloud, DNN, Machine Learning

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly being used in various applications, including self-driving cars. As with any new technology, it is important to ensure that it is used safely and responsibly. This includes ensuring that AI-powered vehicles are designed and tested in a way that minimizes the risk of accidents and maximizes the safety of passengers and other road users. Additionally, it is important to raise awareness about the capabilities and limitations of AI-powered vehicles among the general public, as well as among those who will be responsible for regulating and overseeing their use. In this introduction, we will discuss the importance of safety and driving awareness in AI applications, specifically in the context of self-driving cars.

The ability to safely and effectively detect and address instances of driving misbehavior relies heavily on the ability to quickly and accurately collect and process relevant data. The current approach used by automotive manufacturers, suppliers, and infrastructure operators involves utilizing multiple data sources, which results in large amounts of data that must be efficiently transferred and processed in a timely manner. Additionally, the actions taken to address these situations often require reliable and fast communication. However, current cellular and Vehicles to Everything (V2X) technologies do not provide the necessary level of real-time and dependable cloud-based detection, analysis, and response for driving misbehavior situations [1].

Misbehavior detection in self-driving cars poses several challenges that must be addressed in order to ensure the safety and reliability of these vehicles. One major challenge is the potential for false positives, which occur when the detection system generates alarms for non-existent problems. These false alarms can be costly and disruptive to the operation of the vehicle. Another challenge is false negatives, which occur when the detection system fails to identify actual misbehavior. This can lead to accidents or other serious incidents. Additionally, self-driving cars are complex systems that involve multiple sensors and

Figure 1 Types of V2X (ref 3GPP 22.885) [2]

software components, which can make it difficult to identify the source of a problem. This complexity can also make it difficult to analyze the large amounts of data that these cars generate. Furthermore, adversaries may try to adapt their behavior to evade detection, which can make it difficult for the detection system to keep up. Finally, the collection of data from the car can raise privacy concerns, as it could potentially be used to track the movements and activities of individuals. Overall, addressing these challenges is crucial for ensuring the safety and reliability of self-driving cars.

Proposed Solution

This paper proposes Misbehavior Detection (MBD) for Safety and Driving awareness.

In AI applications MBD can be a big struggle due to a lack of data and communications requirements in a real-time manner. MBD services enable online sensors and devices through 5G Network as data sharing points to a single Cloud Platform.

MBD service introduced is the Driver Monitoring System (DMS) that uses facial recognition technology via Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) to detect any misbehavior while driving. The system can recognize if the driver is drowsy, distracted, using a cell phone, or smoking. It then sends an immediate alert to the platform if the driver is drowsy, as it is considered the most dangerous condition. For the other three conditions, the system sends a warning to the driver as in Figure 3.

When the DMS system in the vehicle detects a specific event, it initiates a series of actions that start in the vehicle and end in the Cloud through the MEC (Multi-Edge Computing Server). The onboard system identifies the event and sends the related sensor data to the MEC. There, the data is formatted, anonymized, and encrypted to meet the client's requirements. After this process, the data is sent to the Cloud service and received by the third party that is subscribed to this data flow which is in this use case the driver himself, road users, and third-party clients, as depicted in Figure 2.

Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) service refers to the use of automated or connected vehicles, also known as self-driving cars, which have the potential to make transportation systems safer, cleaner, more efficient, and more user-friendly. With the help of 5G-enabled infrastructure, technologies, and vehicles, CAM services include a wide range of digital services. These services are able to communicate with other entities such as other vehicles, roadside infrastructure, pedestrians, and cloud servers through Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication modes, which include Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V), Vehicle-to-Pedestrian (V2P), and Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 2 High-level architecture of the components of this application

Finally, Third Party Service is Parking Lot Detector (PLD) [2]: employing Modena Automotive Smart Area (MASA) cameras to capture real-time video streams and feed it to the PLD in order to generate available parking metadata as a first response to indicate the nearest parking spot available in case of an emergency as illustrated in Figure 4.

Implementation

This section highlights the functionality of different modules within the proposed solution.

Data Collection

The Parking Lot Detector (PLD) module uses smart cameras installed in the MASA, which is a 1 square kilometer area within Modena, Italy. These smart cameras provide full HD live video streams at 30 fps. This acts as an input to the PLD which generates parking metadata which is then sent to the 5GMETA platform. To maintain privacy and security the PLD is deployed as a fog node under the Municipality of Modena GDPR and only the relevant parking metadata is shared outside their network.

The OBU of the connected vehicle provides vehicle telemetry data like its geo-location (latitude and longitude), and vehicle dynamics (speed and heading) as CAM messages in real-time. On-board vehicle sensors (camera and lidar) transmit live H264 encoded video stream and LIDAR point cloud respectively.

The in-vehicle camera sensor used for the DMS system works at 30 fps. Again, to maintain the privacy of the driver, only metadata related to the driver's misbehavior status is shared with the platform. The total volume of the generated data depends on the overall vehicles deployed in the area, and the number of traffic cameras and parking lots monitored.

Driver Monitoring System

The Driver Monitoring System (DMS) is a vision-based software which uses Deep Neural Networks

(DNNs) to identify and detect driving misbehavior based on the facial features of the driver. DMS can assess and categorize if the driver is drowsy, distracted, speaking on a cell phone or smoking (Figure 3). Out of these conditions, drowsiness is considered the highest priority and an *alert* is triggered immediately to the platform to warn about the dangerous driving situation. The other three driver conditions are treated as a *warning* to the driver.

Vehicle On-board Unit with 5G Connectivity

An OBU is mounted on the ADAS-capable vehicle, which captures live telemetry data like geo-location, speed, and heading. This data is then converted to CAM messages and sent to the MEC using a 5G modem. This vehicle data is then further used by other MBD modules. The vehicle also uses camera and LIDAR sensors to provide real-time feedback to the MBD modules about the vehicle’s current trajectory. Video stream and LIDAR point cloud are continuously captured using ROS, and the relevant rosbag¹ is then replayed in order to reproduce similar behavior and situation in which the vehicle was perceiving the surrounding environment.

ADAS/AD System with remote operations support

The vehicle is equipped with a Vehicle Control Unit that allows the car to perform L3-L4 ADAS manoeuvres. This provides the capability to perform an emergency stop if the command is issued or to follow a predetermined path to reach a particular location if its GPS position has already been mapped.

Figure 3 Sample of the DMS application development

¹ <http://wiki.ros.org/rosbag>

Figure 4 Driving Misbehavior information flow

Parking Lot Detector

The PLD system [6] minimizes the associated infrastructure cost in comparison to the traditional sensor-based parking detection system, as it uses camera sensors which are capable to cover large parking spaces.

The PLD is a vision-based application developed to detect parking spaces as well as their occupancy status in real-time on the live video feeds received from the smart cameras installed in the MASA infrastructure. PLD is based on a multi-object detector using YOLOv5 [4] deep neural network (DNN) implementation in PyTorch. The DL model is able to detect and classify road users (cars, trucks, cyclists, etc.) on a live video feed. Along with the object detection algorithm, DeepSORT [5] algorithm is used to keep track of the detected objects in real-time. Objects in the scene (in our case vehicles) are detected and tracked and corresponding bounding boxes are produced in the pixel domain along with their class probability scores as shown in Figure 6 on the left. The detection results are then forwarded to a custom-built Static Object Detection method, which takes the results of all the detections from past T_{sod} frames and determines if the detected object in the scene is a stationary or a moving object. Stationary objects (vehicles) are then checked for N consecutive frames and if they remain in the same spot for a pre-determined time then it is categorized as parked vehicle.

Bounding box pixel coordinates of these parked vehicles are then stored locally which acts as a parking lot database. To determine the current occupancy status of these parking lots another classification model is deployed which is a modified version of AlexNet [3]. Bounding box locations are retrieved from the parking lot database and respective image crops are taken and sent to the classification model. This model then performs binary classification on the image crops and determines if the parking space is occupied or empty. The parking space detection and occupancy classification are designed to work independently to reduce computational overhead and achieve higher efficiency.

All the detected empty spaces are then converted to their relevant GPS coordinates by performing perspective transformation in OpenCV using the pre-calculated homography matrix between the camera image and the geo-referenced bird-eye view of the parking area as shown in Figure 6 on the right. Using the aforementioned approach, PLD can be easily scaled and deployed with convenience on any given centralized or decentralized traffic surveillance system while involving the least amount of manual effort in terms of parking space annotation, as typically seen in other vision-based parking detection systems.

Overall, the proposed method has significant implications for key stakeholders, and it is essential to involve all stakeholders in the deployment process to ensure the successful implementation of the technology.

Future Work

The proposed solution for improving road safety through Misbehaviour Detection and Driving Awareness in connected vehicles with 5G-enabled infrastructure has several challenges.

One major challenge is the requirement for a **large amount of reliable data**, which is crucial for the **accuracy** of AI applications used in the solution. Additionally, the reliability of Driver Monitoring Systems (DMS) can be affected by low lighting conditions, which can further impact the accuracy of the solution.

Furthermore, the installation of specific hardware and software components required for the solution may limit its applicability to certain types of vehicles, which needs to be taken into consideration.

MBD Service #1: Digital twin-based

This module will be developed as a third-party application that would rely on the digital twin of a road segment to detect Wrong-Way Driving (WWD) situations. This MBD module would be developed as a low-latency application, that would run directly on the MEC server that hosts the Digital Twin. The MBD service will directly interact with the Digital Twin through the Digital Twin API. The service would continuously monitor the digital twin road segment by retrieving vehicles' coordinates and mapping them on the MBD map with road direction information. Once any WWD situation is detected, the MBD service would interact with the Digital Twin and trigger a service communicating the dangerous driving event. This action will be seen as a Virtual RSU trigger and will send the ETSI-DENM message over AMQP in charge of signalling the dangerous event to all connected vehicles.

Figure 6 Camera view of a parking area with Yolov5 detections on the left, top view of the same area with metadata shown on the right.

MBD Service #2: Driver Monitoring System (DMS) Client

This module of innovation service is the same that runs currently on the vehicle but would be deployed as a third-party service which can use the live video stream from the DMS system inside the vehicle, to perform driver misbehavior detection.

MBD Service #3: Video-based Wrong Way Driving (WWD) detection

This service will analyse the video streams from the infrastructure cameras and compute the normal flow of the traffic for the different areas of the received image, using algorithms based on object detection, tracking and optical flow. Once its calibration has been computed, a neural network capable of detecting vehicles and tracking their direction will compare the tracked objects against the calculated baseline. In case of divergence, a WWD warning would be raised.

MBR Service #1: Remote Assistance/Management

This service will be developed as a response mechanism to the driving misbehavior detected by the modules discussed before as MBD services. This module will work on the data generated by the Vehicle OBU, DMS and PLD modules in the 5G MEC. As soon as a dangerous situation is triggered by the DMS system, based on the vehicle's current position shared by the vehicle OBU it will gather all the empty spaces provided by the PLD module in the surrounding area. Furthermore, the GPS location of the nearest safe parking space will be sent to the connected vehicle through the platform. As a part of future work in this module, a safe path to the parking space would be computed and shared with the vehicle for it to localize safely in the environment.

MBR Service #2: Traffic Management Centre (TMC) Alerts

This service would be responsible to dispatch alerts to all the vehicles that are near the misbehaving vehicle detected by the MBD modules. It will notify the vehicle's HMI or suggest possible paths to follow in order to avoid the risk.

Conclusion

In this work, the integration of 5G technology in the connected vehicles environment has shown a promising potential to significantly improve road transportation safety. The use of high-speed communication and low-latency capabilities of 5G enables seamless data sharing between connected vehicles, infrastructure, and third-party applications, providing a wealth of reliable real-time data from multiple sources. This real-time data can be used to detect and mitigate driving misbehaviour, facilitate real-time collision avoidance, traffic management, and emergency response. Additionally, the incorporation of 5G technology in CAM services can lead to increased efficiency and reduced costs.

Overall, the use of real-time data and AI applications can lead to a proactive approach to road safety, ultimately saving lives and reducing the overall economic cost associated with accidents. The strategic solution presented in this work highlights the potential of 5G technology to revolutionize the road transportation system, making it safer, more efficient, and more cost-effective. With further research and development, the integration of 5G technology in the connected vehicles environment can lead to a more comprehensive and efficient transportation system that benefits everyone.

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